

YIG/CoFeB Bilayer Magnonic Isolator

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Abstract—We demonstrate a magnonic isolator based on a bilayer structure of yttrium iron garnet (YIG) and cobalt iron boron (CoFeB). The bilayer exhibits pronounced nonreciprocal spin-wave propagation, enabled by dipolar coupling and the magnetic properties of the two layers. The YIG layer provides low damping and efficient spin-wave propagation, whereas the CoFeB layer introduces strong magnetic anisotropy, critical for achieving the isolator functionality. Experimental results, supported by numerical simulations, show unidirectional propagation of magneto-static surface spin waves, significantly suppressing backscattered waves. This behavior was confirmed through wavevector-resolved and microfocused Brillouin light scattering measurements and is supported by numerical simulations. The developed YIG/SiO₂/CoFeB bilayer magnonic isolator demonstrates the feasibility of leveraging nonreciprocal spin-wave dynamics for functional magnonic devices, paving the way for energy-efficient, wave-based signal processing technologies.

Index Terms—Nanomagnetics, magnonics, nonreciprocity, spin waves.

I. INTRODUCTION

Magnon-based devices have been of great interest in recent decades due to their unique ability to leverage magnons, the quanta of spin waves, as information carriers. One of the key advantages of magnons lies in their low-energy consumption, their frequencies that can reach the terahertz range [Wu 2017], and their wavelengths that can reach down to the lattice constant [Barman 2021, Chumak 2022]. These properties make magnonic devices highly promising for achieving extreme miniaturization in future technologies. Furthermore, the tunability of spin-wave dispersion provides a powerful tool for engineering nonreciprocal behavior, allowing spin waves to propagate with different characteristics in opposite directions. The nonreciprocal propagation of spin waves can be induced and controlled through various mechanisms, such as the nonreciprocal behavior of magneto-static surface spin waves (MSSWs) in ferrite slabs that are magnetized at only one side [Seshadri 1970] or through utilizing curvilinear three-dimensional structures [Hertel 2013, Pylypovskiy 2015, Sheka 2015, Otálora 2016, Pylypovskiy 2016] or employing magnetic systems dominated by the Dzyaloshinskii–Moriya interaction [Dzyaloshinsky 1958, Moriya 1960, Nembach 2015, Tacchi 2017, dos Santos 2020]. Another method is the use of magnetic bilayers in a parallel magnetization

state [Gallardo 2019b, Gerevenkov 2023], antiparallel magnetization state [Grünberg 1986, Gallardo 2019a], or in the form of a synthetic antiferromagnet (SAF) [Verba 2019, Wojewoda 2024b]. For example, a cobalt iron boron (CoFeB)/Permalloy(Py) exchange-coupled bilayer was demonstrated numerically and experimentally as a magnonic diode, where the exchange coupling facilitated nonreciprocal propagation [Grassi 2020]. Spin-wave nonreciprocity is particularly beneficial for developing functionalities, such as magnonic isolators, circulators, and diodes, which are essential components in advanced signal processing and computing systems [Verba 2013, Gladii 2016, Yu 2016]. These attributes position magnon-based devices as a compelling platform for energy-efficient, scalable, and reconfigurable information technologies.

Here, we present the experimental realization of a magnonic isolator based on a magnetic bilayer of yttrium iron garnet (YIG)/cobalt iron boron (YIG/CoFeB), coupled via dipolar interaction through a nonmagnetic spacer of SiO₂. Unlike exchange-coupled systems, such as CoFeB/Py bilayers [Grassi 2020], the dipolar coupling in our system preserves the low damping of YIG, with values remaining in the range of 10⁻⁴, facilitating extended spin-wave propagation lengths. The broken spatial symmetry along the thickness causes nonreciprocal propagation when MSSWs are excited by transverse in-plane magnetization. The spin-wave nonreciprocity arises from the dynamic dipolar field interaction between the two magnetically heterogeneous layers, which exhibit distinct magnetic properties, such

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as saturation magnetization M_s , propagation frequency f , phase ϕ , and group velocities. Under these conditions, the spin waves propagating in the two layers, with different distributions of dynamic magnetization and phases, create stray fields that interact dynamically. These stray fields interact with the dynamic magnetization in each layer. This interaction modifies the dynamic dipolar interaction energy density, $\epsilon_d = -\frac{\mu_0}{2} \mathbf{m} \cdot \mathbf{h}_{\text{stray}}$ [Gallardo 2019a], making it nonreciprocal with respect to the spin-wave propagation direction. The energy density is minimized when m and h_{stray} are parallel and maximized when they are antiparallel. Larger disparities between the magnetic properties of the two layers amplify this nonreciprocity, which was validated with numerical simulations and experimentally using wavevector-resolved Brillouin light scattering (k -BLS) spectroscopy for nonreciprocal dispersion investigation and microfocused μ -BLS for spin-wave transport measurements.

This pronounced nonreciprocal behavior underscores the potential of YIG/CoFeB-based bilayers for magnonic isolators, phase shifters, and other wave-based signal processing devices.

II. METHODS AND MATERIALS

A. Materials

The YIG film used is 100 nm thick grown on a 500 μm thick gadolinium gallium garnet (GGG) substrate using liquid phase epitaxy [Dubs 2017, 2020]. We used magnetron sputtering to grow a 5 nm thick SiO_2 (nonmagnetic spacer) and the ferromagnetic layer of 40 nm thick CoFeB on the YIG film—see Fig. 1(a). This magnetic stack of YIG(100 nm)/ SiO_2 (5 nm)/CoFeB(40 nm) was characterized using vector network analyzer ferromagnetic resonance (VNA-FMR) spectroscopy [Maksymov 2015] to extract the YIG material parameters within the stack, based on the quasi YIG peak characterization where only the low-frequency peak (corresponding to YIG) is considered, which showed an effective magnetization $M_{\text{eff}} = (160.1 \pm 0.3)$ kA/m, an inhomogeneous linewidth broadening $\mu_0 \Delta H_0 = (0.161 \pm 0.02)$ mT, and Gilbert damping coefficient $\alpha = (4.4 \pm 0.02) \times 10^{-4}$. A plain YIG film cut from the same sample wafer was characterized using VNA-FMR spectroscopy, and a Gilbert damping coefficient of $\alpha = (7.7 \pm 0.65) \times 10^{-5}$ was measured, which is almost one order of magnitude smaller than that in the magnetic bilayer. The damping in the YIG/CoFeB bilayer (without a nonmagnetic spacer) was investigated, showing a significant broadening of the linewidth: 1.12 mT at an external field of 10 mT compared to 0.18 mT at 14 mT in the YIG/ SiO_2 /CoFeB bilayer (not shown for brevity). This behavior qualitatively aligns with the findings in Qin [2018], where direct exchange coupling between YIG and a ferromagnetic metallic layer facilitates dynamic exchange torque at the interface. The enhanced damping in such bilayers arises from this exchange interaction, which not only transfers angular momentum but also allows for the efficient excitation of higher order standing modes, particularly near the ferromagnetic resonance frequencies of either layer constituting the bilayer.

To excite and detect coherent spin waves using μ -BLS, we fabricated a 600 nm wide microwave strip antenna via electron-beam lithography. The antenna is composed of a Ti(5 nm)/ SiO_2 (10 nm)/Ti(5 nm)/Au(80 nm) stack deposited by electron beam evaporation.

Fig. 1. (a) Schematics of the nanometer-thick magnetic bilayer of GGG/YIG(100 nm)/ SiO_2 (5 nm)/CoFeB(40 nm). (b) Dispersion relations of MSSWs in the magnetic bilayer film simulated numerically using MuMax³, shown as a color map, where red is maximum spin-wave intensity and blue is zero intensity. The square symbols represent the experimental data of spin-wave frequency f as a function of wavevector k measured on the same bilayer film with wavevector-resolved BLS (k -resolved), including the error bars.

B. Micromagnetic Simulations

To choose the material and thickness of the second magnetic layer of the bilayer, a micromagnetic simulation study was performed using the GPU-accelerated program MuMax³ [Vansteenkiste 2014]. For the nanometer-thick bilayer of YIG/ SiO_2 /CoFeB, a length $x = 40 \mu\text{m}$, width $y = 100$ nm, and thickness $t = 145$ nm are considered. The periodic boundary conditions $\text{PBC} = (10, 100, 0)$ are applied along the length and width to mimic a thin plane film. The cell size was set to (10 nm \times 10 nm) in the in-plane direction and to 5 nm in the out-of-plane direction, to account for the nonmagnetic spacer SiO_2 . The material parameters used for YIG are saturation magnetization $M_s = 140$ kA/m (without taking into account the anisotropy fields), exchange constant $A_{\text{ex}} = 3.5$ pJ/m, and $\alpha = 2 \times 10^{-4}$; for SiO_2 are $M_s = 0$ kA/m, $A_{\text{ex}} = 0$ pJ/m, and $\alpha = 1$; and lastly, for CoFeB are $M_s = 1250$ kA/m, $A_{\text{ex}} = 15$ pJ/m, and $\alpha = 4 \times 10^{-3}$. A sinc-function pulse in time excites spin waves in the in-plane transverse direction.

C. BLS Measurements

BLS spectroscopy [Sebastian 2015] relies on the process of inelastic scattering of light as a result of photon-magnon interaction, while conserving the in-plane momentum. This inelastic light-scattering can create or annihilate a magnon, resulting in Stokes and anti-Stokes peaks

in the BLS spectrum. The momentum of detected magnons is given by $k_{\text{magnon}} = \frac{4\pi}{\lambda_L} \sin \theta$, where λ_L is the incident laser wavelength and θ is the incident angle of the laser. The frequencies of the inelastically scattered light are analyzed using a tandem Fabry–Pérot interferometer (TFPI) [Mock 1987].

To validate the micromagnetic simulations and the nonreciprocal behavior of the magnetic bilayer, k -resolved BLS measurements were performed. The measurements are done in the Damon–Eshbach configuration to measure MSSWs where the bias magnetic field is applied along the sample plane but perpendicular to the incident laser beam plane. The monochromatic laser used is of wavelength $\lambda_L = 491$ nm. The k resolution comes from changing the incidence angle of the laser beam in the range of 2.5° to 80° , which corresponds to $k_{\text{magnon}} = 1.1163$ to 25.205 rad/ μm . The thermal signal was recorded for both polarities of the bias field of 200 mT.

The microfocused μ -BLS is used to measure coherent spin waves and validate nonreciprocal propagation. A continuous-wave, monochromatic polarized laser beam of $\lambda_L = 457$ nm is used. The laser is focused through the GGG substrate onto the YIG film, using a cover glass corrected objective. This objective lens, with a numerical aperture of 0.85, achieves a focal spot diameter d of 330 nm when used with λ_L . This configuration enables the detection of wavevectors up to 12 rad/ μm [Wojewoda 2024a].

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The numerical simulation of the nanometer-thick magnetic bilayer GGG/YIG(100 nm)/SiO₂(5 nm)/CoFeB(40 nm) is shown in Fig. 1(b) as a color map. It depicts the dispersion relations of MSSWs in the YIG film as part of the stack at a 200 mT bias field. The dispersion curve shows pronounced frequency nonreciprocity for counterpropagating surface waves. Specifically, in the $-k$ propagation direction, the surface waves behave like backward-volume magneto-static spin waves, where the slope of the dispersion curve is negative in the small k limit and becomes zero around $k = -10$ rad/ μm . In this range, the group velocity is negative and reaches zero at $k = -10$ rad/ μm , while the phase velocity remains positive. This results in the group velocity and phase velocity pointing in opposite directions for wavevectors between -10 and 0 rad/ μm . Such behavior highlights the unique nonreciprocal spin-wave dynamics in the bilayer structure. These simulations suggest, that in this magnetic bilayer, MSSWs of wavevectors $k = \pm 10$ rad/ μm are unidirectional. By adjusting the thickness of the CoFeB magnetic layer, we were able to achieve such a flat frequency plateau in only one direction [Grassi 2020]. Similar to the phenomenon measured in SAFs [Wojewoda 2024b], we deduce from our simulations that zero momentum waves in the bilayer can propagate as they do not exhibit zero group velocities.

The dispersion curve of MSSW in the fabricated magnetic bilayer film was measured using k -resolved BLS. The experimental results are shown as the square symbols in Fig. 1(b) on top of the simulated color map. There is an agreement between the experimental data and the simulations with a slight shift in frequencies that can be explained by the fact that the fabricated bilayer thicknesses could be slightly inaccurate. Nevertheless, the nonreciprocal dispersion behavior is conserved and matches very well what was found in simulations. The gaps seen in the experimental data correspond to the phonon modes measured in

Fig. 2. Schematics of the experimental setup micro-focused (μ -BLS) and SEM micrograph of the structure under investigation. A magnetic bias field of $\mu_0 H_{\text{ext}} = 200$ mT is applied perpendicular (along the y -direction) to the wave propagation (along the x -direction). Spin waves are excited through a continuous RF signal of power $P = 5$ dBm into the microstrip antenna.

the sample. As noted above, these data were collected by measuring the spin-wave signal while varying the incident laser angle with respect to the sample plane at both polarities of the magnetic field (± 200 mT). While it is typically sufficient to measure the Stokes and anti-Stokes peaks at one field polarity to capture the spin waves propagating in opposite directions, measurements at both polarities were performed here because the reference signal position shifted slightly when the field polarity was reversed. By combining data from both polarities, this reference shift could be compensated, allowing for more accurate error estimation.

The schematic of the μ -BLS experimental setup together with a scanning electron microscopy (SEM) image of the sample is shown in Fig. 2. We used the microstrip microwave antenna on the nanometer-thick magnetic bilayer film to excite coherent spin waves propagating perpendicular to the applied bias magnetic field of ± 200 mT. We applied a continuous-wave radio frequency (RF) signal of power $P = 5$ dBm through the microstrip antenna. The setup uses a monochromatic blue laser that is focused on the sample through an objective lens. A polarized beam cube is used to pass only the photons that were inelastically scattered on magnons to the six-pass TFPI, which uses two mirror pairs. After the frequencies are analyzed in the TFPI, the light is guided to a photodetector.

Fig. 3. (a) Normalized BLS intensity as a function of laser position in the x -direction with regards to the antenna position dependent on the applied bias field for an excitation frequency of 7.23 GHz. Spin wave spectra measured at distances of (b) 4 μm and (c) 8 μm from the microstrip antenna.

We performed the measurements using the μ -BLS in the form of a one-dimensional (**1-D**) line scan along the x -direction that starts at the antenna position with 500 nm steps. The 1-D line scan was repeated for the two polarities of the magnetic field ± 200 mT on the same side of the antenna, as shown in Fig. 2. The results of the line scans are shown in Fig. 3(a) in terms of normalized BLS intensity as a function of x -position with regard to the antenna position at an excitation frequency of 7.23 GHz. This excitation frequency was selected as it generated the strongest coherent signal observed during the measurements. The BLS intensity is proportional to the spin-wave intensity. We normalized each line scan to its own to eliminate the nonreciprocity effect caused by the nonreciprocal excitation efficiency characteristic of the Damon–Eshbach configuration. The position $x = 0 \mu\text{m}$ is at the bottom of the antenna, and $x = 0.5 \mu\text{m}$ is just outside the 600 nm wide antenna. The decay length λ was extracted by fitting the data to an exponential decay model $I = I_0 \exp(-2x/\lambda)$. The first three data points were excluded from the fit of both polarity line scans as they correspond to positions directly under or very near the antenna. These points are influenced by both propagation directions and potentially nonresonant modes, which contribute to the measured counts. We excluded the data points after $x = 10 \mu\text{m}$ of the -200 mT field line scan as well since they reach the thermal level. The decay length λ of spin waves in the positive field direction was measured to be nearly three times that of spin waves in the opposite field polarity, with values of $\lambda_{+200\text{mT}} = 10.92 \mu\text{m}$ and $\lambda_{-200\text{mT}} = 3.78 \mu\text{m}$.

Fig. 3(b) and (c) shows the spin-wave spectra measured at 4 and 8 μm away from the antenna, respectively. The spin waves excited at a -200 mT bias field drop to below 1000 counts compared to almost 14×10^3 at the opposite polarity field—see the spin-wave spectrum in Fig. 3(b). Further away from the antenna at $x = 8 \mu\text{m}$, the spin waves are at the thermal level with counts way below 500 at -200 mT, while at

$+200$ mT, spin waves were still detected with more than 3000 counts, as shown in Fig. 3(c). These results demonstrate the unidirectional nature of spin-wave propagation in our nanometer-thick magnetic bilayer, with significantly longer decay lengths at $+200$ mT compared to -200 mT. The bilayer’s ability to support long-distance spin-wave propagation (over 10 μm) and its strong asymmetry in propagation directions establish it as an effective magnonic isolator, capable of directional spin-wave transport. Beyond its role as a magnonic isolator, the bilayer’s strong nonreciprocity and long spin-wave propagation length make it a promising platform for RF, binary, and neuromorphic computing. In RF applications, spin-wave devices are gaining interest, particularly for compact and efficient nonreciprocal components, such as isolators and Y-circulators [Levchenko 2024]. A key challenge continues to be the magnon transducer efficiency, which impacts insertion losses [Davidková 2025]. However, recent advances have reduced losses to as little as 3 dB [Erdélyi 2024, Bruckner 2025], greatly enhancing the feasibility of magnonic RF devices. To ensure practical deployment, it is crucial to focus on scalability, optimize transducers, and integrate them with semiconductor technologies.

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